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Behavioral and electrophysiological correlates of interactions
between grouping principles in touch: Evidence from
psychophysical indirect tasks

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Abstract

In two experiments we investigated the behavioral and brain correlates of the interactions between spatial-proximity and texture-similarity grouping principles in touch. We designed two adaptations of the repetition discrimination task (RDT) previously used in vision. This task provides an indirect measure of grouping that does not require explicit attention to the grouping process. In Experiment 1, participants were presented with a row of elements alternating in texture except for one pair in which the same texture was repeated. The participants had to decide whether the repeated texture stimuli (similarity grouping) were smooth or rough, while the spatial proximity between targets and distractors was varied either to facilitate or hinder the response. In Experiment 2, participants indicated which cohort (proximity grouping) contained more elements, while texture-similarity within and between cohorts was modified. The results indicated additive effects of grouping cues in which proximity dominated the perceptual grouping process when the two principles acted together. In addition, the independent component analysis (ICA) performed on electrophysiological data revealed the implication of a widespread network of sensorimotor, prefrontal, parietal and occipital brain areas in both experiments.

Keywords: Perceptual organization; proximity; similarity; grouping, touch

1 **1. Introduction**

2 Perceptual grouping plays a key role in the process of extracting information from
3 the raw perceptual input, according to certain *cues* like shared features or spatial
4 arrangement, and bound it together into an integrated percept (Schmidt & Schmidt,
5 2013). While the question was first discussed and experimentally addressed by
6 Wertheimer (1923) in the context of Gestalt psychology (see Vezzani, Marino & Giora,
7 2012), it was not until the second half of the 20th century that it was considered from
8 the perspective of the cognitive psychology. The focus then was on the description of
9 new grouping principles (e.g: Palmer, 1992), the quantitative measure of grouping, and
10 the development of laws and models to account for grouping effects (Kubovy & van
11 den Berg, 2008).

12 Most of the studies addressing the principles of perceptual grouping have been
13 conducted on vision and audition (see Wagemans, Elder, et al., 2012; Wagemans,
14 Feldman, et al., 2012 for extensive reviews). However, there has been increasing
15 interest in the investigation and application of perceptual grouping to the haptic
16 modality (see Gallace and Spence, 2011, for a review of the history of perceptual
17 grouping in tactile perception). For example, Overvliet, Krampe, and Wagemans (2012,
18 2013) found that contour detection and haptic search are influenced by proximity and
19 similarity grouping principles, respectively. More recently, Verlaers, Wagemans, and
20 Overvliet (2015) and Overvliet and Plaisier (2016) reported that proximity grouping and
21 configural cues speed up haptic enumeration. Thus, it seems that the tactile perceptual
22 system organizes the information acquired by touch following laws and mechanisms
23 similar to those used by other sensory modalities. In particular, Chang, Nesbitt, and
24 Wilkins (2007a, 2007b) found that their participants grouped visual and tactile patterns
25 in almost the same way. This is in agreement with previous research in the haptic

1 modality, which found similarities and shared mechanisms between vision and touch in
2 a number of perceptual phenomena and cognitive processes, such as symmetry detection
3 (Ballesteros & Reales, 2004), perceptual illusions (Ballesteros, Mayas, Reales, &
4 Heller, 2012), haptic priming (Ballesteros & Reales, 2005).

5 In vision, considerable attention has focused on the interactions between different
6 grouping principles when multiple cues act conjoined within the same stimulus; in other
7 words, when the grouping principles act in *cooperation* (i.e., when grouping principles
8 are conjoined in cooperation, strengthening certain stimulus configurations) and in
9 *competition* (i.e., when principles are conjoined in competition against each other,
10 strengthening different stimulus configurations) compared to when they act alone
11 (Kubovy & van den Berg, 2008; Quinlan & Wilton, 1998). The results of these studies
12 show that the grouping effects are stronger when the grouping principles cooperate.
13 Moreover, when grouping principles compete, the grouping effect is weaker and
14 unstable compared to their acting alone effect. Interestingly, Kubovy and van den Berg
15 (2008) proposed an additive model of grouping effects that accounted for the results
16 obtained in the visual modality. According to the authors, additive effects can be
17 inferred when: (1) the grouping strength under *cooperation* conditions is greater than
18 the grouping strength of each principle in isolation; and (2) the grouping strength under
19 *competition* conditions is weaker than the grouping strength of each individual
20 principle. The interaction between grouping principles in touch has also been addressed
21 at least in two different studies. Frings and Spence (2013) investigated the influence of
22 Gestalt grouping on the ability to ignore distracting tactile information using a negative-
23 priming paradigm. Their results indicated that the presence of negative priming was
24 influenced by the interaction of the grouping principles of connectedness and proximity.
25 Moreover, in a recent behavioral study (Prieto, Mayas, & Ballesteros, 2018b), we

1 adapted two different phenomenological and psychophysical tasks previously employed
2 in the visual modality (Luna, Villalba-García, Montoro, & Hinojosa, 2016; Quinlan &
3 Wilton, 1998). Our results in the haptic modality showed a similar pattern of
4 interactions those found in visual modality regarding (1) the conjoined effect grouping
5 principles and (2) the compatibility with the additive model outlined above.

6 Other researchers have investigated the neural substrates of the interactions
7 between the grouping principles in the visual modality. For example, Han (2004)
8 recorded event-related potentials (ERPs) while observers performed an orientation
9 identification task in which the grouping cues were congruent or incongruent.
10 Responses were faster to proximity-based orientation discrimination. In addition,
11 responses were slowed by incongruent cues, and this effect was larger when the
12 observers had to identify the orientation based on similarity cues while ignoring
13 proximity. ERPs showed enhanced positivity over temporo-parietal areas in the 180-220
14 ms time window only under similarity conditions. These electrophysiological results
15 provide evidence of the dominance of proximity over similarity grouping cues.
16 However, the results should be taken with caution, as the relative strength of the
17 grouping cues had not been equated. In a later work, Nikolaev, Gepshtein, Kubovy and
18 Van Leeuwen (2008) varied the relative salience of the competing perceptual
19 organizations using a phenomenological task,. Their results indicate that the ability to
20 discriminate between competing organizations was correlated with the amplitude of C1
21 and P1 peaks. Regarding the haptic modality, Prieto, Mayas, & Ballesteros, (2018a)
22 conducted a recent study to investigate the oscillatory brain activity of proximity and
23 similarity grouping principles acting in isolation (not conjoined) using an orientation
24 detection task adapted from one used previously in vision and touch (Han, 2004; Prieto,
25 Mayas, & Ballesteros, 2014). Their analysis focused in the event related changes of the

1 alpha and beta band frequencies within the sensorimotor and parietal areas which
2 constitute the main components off the sensorimotor rhythm. Their behavioral results
3 indicate that responses to proximity grouping were faster and more accurate than those
4 to similarity grouping. In addition, they found the activation of a network of widely
5 distributed sensorimotor and parietal areas that seem to be involved in the haptic
6 grouping process. Unfortunately, there is no previous empirical evidence addressing the
7 neural correlates of the interaction between grouping principles in the tactile modality.
8 To date, there have been only a few indirect approaches to the topic (e.g. Blankenburg,
9 Ruff, Deichmann, Rees, & Driver, 2006).

10 Given the lack of studies addressing the neurophysiological correlates of the
11 interactions between different grouping principles in touch, the present study aimed to
12 investigate the behavioral and brain (electroencephalographic, EEG) dynamics of the
13 interactions when two grouping principles are conjoined either cooperatively or
14 competitively. To achieve this objective, we conducted two experiments comparing two
15 grouping principles, spatial proximity and texture similarity, in the haptic modality. The
16 traditional paradigms used to measure the grouping effects of the interactions between
17 grouping principles and the additivity of the grouping process, usually involve tasks
18 requiring either a phenomenological report of the strength of the grouping (Quinlan &
19 Wilton, 1998) or selectively attend to a grouping cue and perform speeded responses to
20 indicate the perceived organization (Luna, Villalba-García, Montoro, & Hinojosa,
21 2016). The latter task introduces an objective, physically defined correct response,
22 rather than a purely phenomenological one. This allows the assessment of performance
23 (accuracy and response times) and of response bias against an objectively defined
24 correct response, eliminating the possibility of spontaneous grouping without knowing
25 what should be perceived. This could lead to the use of alternative strategies not related

1 to grouping itself (Kubovy & Gepshtein, 2003). To avoid this problem, Palmer and
2 Beck (2007) developed the repetition discrimination task (RDT), an indirect measure of
3 grouping that does not require explicit attention to a grouping cue. The advantages of
4 the RDT are: (1) that it provides a physically defined correct response, suitable to
5 generate quantitative measures of grouping under speeded performance conditions; and
6 (2) that it is apparently unrelated to grouping, preventing the strategic effects of directed
7 attention tasks.

8 For the present study we designed two touch adaptations of the original RDT.
9 These indirect haptic tasks require neither explicit attention to the grouping cues nor any
10 knowledge about the purpose of the task. Importantly, the relative strengths of the
11 grouping cues were equated by means of a phenomenological task in which participants
12 rated the perceived strength of each grouping principle and their interactions (see Prieto,
13 Mayas, & Ballesteros, 2018a). This ensured that any differences in the interaction
14 pattern between the two grouping principles could not be attributable to the salience of a
15 single cue.

16 In addition, to investigate the neural correlates (time/frequency oscillatory brain
17 activity) of the interactions between grouping principles, we followed the same
18 procedure previously used in touch by Prieto et al., (2018a) and employed independent
19 component analysis (ICA) (Bell & Sejnowski, 1995) and independent component (IC)
20 clustering to focus on alpha (8-14 Hz) and beta (15-25 Hz) band event-related spectral
21 perturbations (ERSP) within the sensorimotor cortex, which constitute the main
22 components of the mu (μ) sensorimotor rhythm (SMR) (Vukelić et al., 2014). The
23 enhancement and suppression of alpha-band power is considered an indicator of cortical
24 inhibition/activation respectively, and is particularly useful to measure sensorimotor
25 activity (Klimesch, Sauseng, & Hanslmayr, 2007; Melnik, Hairston, Ferris, & König,

1 2017). Beta band (ERSP), on the other hand, is associated with motor
2 activity/performance and top-down sensory analysis (Boonstra, Daffertshofer,
3 Breakspear, & Beek, 2007). Thus, the combination of μ -alpha and beta spectral changes
4 could provide important information about haptic perceptual grouping. Additionally, we
5 also focused on frontal and parietal ERSP as a marker of conflict resolution between
6 competing cues (West, Jakubek, Wymbs, Perry, & Moore, 2005).

7 Based on previous findings obtained in vision and touch regarding the dominance
8 of proximity (Han, 2004; Prieto et al., 2014, 2018a, 2018b)), as well as in the
9 similarities between these two modalities in perceptual grouping (Chang et al., 2007b,
10 2007a), we expected that proximity would dominate haptic grouping. Overall, we
11 expected slower response times (RTs) and greater interference/facilitatory effects under
12 competitive/cooperative conditions respectively when proximity was the interfering
13 feature (Experiment 1, targets grouped by similarity). By contrast, we hypothesized
14 slower RTs and less or no facilitation/interference at all when similarity was the
15 interfering feature (Experiment 2, targets grouped by proximity). In addition, we
16 hypothesized that the interactive effects of the grouping principles would be compatible
17 with an additive model of grouping effects (Kubovy and van den Berg, 2008); in other
18 words, (1) greater grouping strength under cooperative conditions compared to the
19 strength of each principle in isolation, and (2) weaker grouping strength under
20 competition conditions compared to the strength of each principle alone.

21 Regarding the analysis of the ERSP, we expected the activation of a bilateral
22 network of sensorimotor areas, that would be reflected in a power decrease (event-
23 related desynchronization or ERD) of the alpha and beta bands over those regions
24 during the task period (Melnik et al., 2017; Prieto et al., 2018a). We also hypothesized
25 that conditions under which the two principles compete would lead to increased activity

1 in frontal and parietal regions, traditionally associated with conflict processing and
2 conflict resolution (Cohen & Ridderinkhof, 2013), especially when proximity was the
3 interfering cue (Experiment 1), in accordance with the dominance of proximity expected
4 in our behavioral hypotheses.

5

6 **2. Experiment 1**

7 Experiment 1 tested the influence of grouping by spatial proximity over the
8 detection of targets based on texture similarity. Participants had to identify the repeated
9 texture (target grouped by similarity) in a row of seven elements that alternated in
10 texture. Proximity cues could either facilitate (cooperation condition) or hinder
11 (competition condition) task performance.

12 *2.1. Method*

13 *2.1.1. Participants*

14 Twenty-one volunteer students (6 males; age range: 20-52, mean age = 34.60, SD =
15 9.24) from the Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia (UNED) participated in
16 Experiment 1. All reported being right-handed, had normal tactile perception and were
17 naïve to the purpose of the experiment. All the participants completed the Spanish
18 adaptation of the Edinburgh Handedness Inventory (Oldfield, 1971) and signed an
19 informed consent form for participation in the study. The experimental protocol was
20 approved by the Ethics Committee of the Universidad Nacional de Educación a
21 Distancia and was in accordance with the ethical standards of the Declaration of
22 Helsinki (Williams, 2008).

23 *2.1.2. Apparatus and stimuli*

24 We used a specially designed haptic device (Haptic Monitor, MonHap) for stimulus
25 presentation and data acquisition (see Figure 1 left). The device consisted of an

1 electromagnetically shielded (to avoid possible EEG artifacts) opaque box with two
2 platforms containing an array of 10 x 10 sockets in which the tactile stimuli were
3 plugged to create the desired configuration. The device had two apertures for the hands,
4 enabling either single or bimanual exploration of the tactile patterns. The MonHap was
5 interfaced with two different computers; one controlled the experimental sequence and
6 stimulus presentation, and recorded responses and exploration times, and the other was
7 used for the acquisition of EEG data.

8 The stimuli consisted of a series of touch-sensitive cylinders, each measuring 13
9 mm (height) x 15 mm (diameter), specifically designed for use in the MonHap device
10 (Figure 1 right). The top surface of half of the cylinders was covered with sandpaper to
11 create a rough texture. The other half had a smooth metallic texture. In each trial, the
12 cylinders were arranged in a single row of seven elements to form 18 different stimuli
13 configurations for three different conditions (see Figure 2). In cooperative trials, the
14 targets were spatially close to each other (6 mm apart) and separated from the rest of the
15 cylinders (24 mm), while in competitive trials, the targets were proximal to the
16 distractors and non-proximal to each other. Finally, single (neutral) trials were those in
17 which all the cylinders (targets and distractors) were equally spaced.

1

2 **Fig. 1.** Left: An overall view of the Haptic monitor. Right: Schematic representation of
3 the individual touch-sensitive elements that formed the haptic displays.

1. Similarity only (single)

2. Combined grouping principles (Cooperation)

3. Combined grouping principles (Competition)

1

2 **Fig. 2.** Representation of the three experimental conditions used in Experiment 1: (1)
 3 similarity acting alone; (2) cooperation between grouping principles, and (3)
 4 competition between grouping principles. The circles inside the box are the target
 5 stimuli.

6

7 2.1.3. Design and procedure

8 We used a 3 x 3 repeated measures design with two within-subject factors: 3

9 grouping conditions (cooperative, competitive, single) and 3 target positions (3/4, 4/5;

1 5/6). Response times from the first contact with the stimulus to the onset of the response
2 and error rates were the dependent variables.

3 The experiment was conducted individually inside an electromagnetically shielded
4 room of our laboratory. The participant received verbal instructions at the beginning of
5 the experimental session. Once she/he was seated inside the experimental cabin, further
6 instructions appeared on the computer screen. The task was to indicate as fast and
7 accurately as possible if the repeated texture was rough or smooth. Participants explored
8 the row of elements sequentially (from right to left) with their right hand and responded
9 by pressing one of the two foot pedals (one for “smooth” and the other for “rough”) that
10 were counterbalanced across participants. The total number of trials was 108 (36 per
11 condition), conducted in a single block that lasted approximately 40-50 minutes.

12 Participants were seated in front of the haptic device with their right hand inside the
13 right aperture of the apparatus. To minimize muscular artifacts produced by arm and
14 body movements, they were instructed to put their forearms inside the device, and to
15 rest comfortably on the back of the chair. The experimenter guided the hand of the
16 participant to the start position at the beginning of each trial (the index and middle
17 fingers of the right hand placed on the right side of the haptic display without touching
18 it). Then, the experimenter signaled the start of the trial verbally. Participants were
19 instructed to place their index and middle fingers on the surface of the first element of
20 the row, to explore the pattern sequentially at a constant speed without going back and
21 to respond as fast and accurately as possible using the foot pedals. In addition, the
22 beginning of the trial (in terms of response time recording and EEG triggering) was
23 initiated automatically by the first contact of the participant’s hand with the stimulus, as
24 all cylinders were touch sensitive. At the end of the trial, the participant returned the
25 hand to the start position and the computer automatically displayed the next randomly

1 generated stimulus on the computer screen. The experimenter then configured the next
2 trial by plugging the cylinders into the presentation platform. This procedure was
3 repeated until the end of the experiment. Participants completed 10 practice trials before
4 the start of the experimental session to ensure that they understood the experimental
5 procedure.

6 2.1.4. EEG acquisition and pre-processing

7 We used a 34-channel elasticized cap with Ag/AgCl sintered electrodes (Neuroscan
8 Medical supplies Inc.) to register EEG data from scalp electrodes (FP1, FP2, F7, F3,
9 FZ, F4, F8, FT9, FT7, FC3, FCZ, FC4, FT8, FT10, T3, C3, CZ, C4, T4, TP7, CP3,
10 CPZ, CP4, TP8, T5, P3, PZ, P4, T6, PO1, PO2, O1, OZ, O2) positioned according to
11 the extended international 10-20 system. Vertical (VEOG) and horizontal (HEOG) were
12 recorded in two bipolar channels to control for ocular artifacts. Blinks and vertical
13 artifacts were monitored via electrodes below and above the orbital ridge of the left eye.
14 Horizontal artifacts were monitored through electrodes located on the outer canthus of
15 each eye. Participants were grounded to the AFz electrode, and linked mastoids (A1,
16 A2) were used as the online reference. A NuAmps amplifier (Neuroscan Inc.) was used
17 to digitize the data. Sampling rate was set at 250 Hz, overall impedance was maintained
18 below 10k Ω throughout the experimental procedure, and channels were online band-
19 pass (0.1-70 Hz) and notch filtered (50 Hz) to eliminate power line and other artifacts.
20 Prior to the start of the experiment, participants were shown their EEG on the screen
21 and instructed how to avoid head and body movement artifacts.

22 Offline pre-processing of the EEG recordings was carried out under Matlab
23 environment (The MathWorks, Inc), using the EEGLAB toolbox (Delorme & Makeig,
24 2004). Continuous raw data were filtered using a digital FIR (finite impulse response)
25 filter (0.5-40 Hz; Order 32). We used the lowest order that eliminates low and high

1 frequency artifacts while preserving target frequencies, in order to remove the
2 maximum amount of noise while causing the minimum distortion of the data. After
3 filtering, continuous EEG data were divided into baseline corrected and non-overlapped
4 epochs ranging from 1000 ms before to 4000 ms after the start of exploration (the first
5 contact of the fingers with the haptic display), with the pre-stimulus (-1000-0) interval
6 as the baseline period. Epochs containing high amplitude/frequency and other irregular
7 artifacts were removed by visual inspection. After that, artifact-free epochs were
8 selected for averaging (Mean = 85 epochs per participant; Min/Max = 75-97).
9 Importantly, the existence of ocular movements and/or muscular artifacts was not a
10 criterion for epoch rejection. Instead, they were removed using Infomax Independent
11 Component Analysis (ICA) decomposition (Bell & Sejnowski, 1995). Details of the
12 ICA analysis are described in section 2.2.2.

13 2.2. Data analysis

14 2.2.1. Behavioral data

15 Two dependent measures were used to evaluate behavioral performance: (1) mean
16 response times (RTs) for correct responses, computed as the time between the first
17 contact with the stimulus and the pressing of the foot pedal; and (2) accuracy of the
18 task, computed as the proportion of errors in each condition. Two separate repeated
19 measures ANOVAs with 3 *grouping conditions* (cooperative, competitive, neutral) x 3
20 *target positions* (3/4, 4/5, 5/6) were conducted on RTs and accuracy, respectively. RT
21 analysis was conducted only on correct responses within 3 standard deviations above
22 and below the mean (7.62 % trials removed). All the statistical tests were Bonferroni
23 corrected.

24

25

2.2.2. Independent component analysis (ICA) and component clustering

To avoid the confound derived from the mixed EEG signals recorded from the scalp, we used EEGLAB to perform s ICA (Bell & Sejnowski, 1995) on the EEG data. This enabled us to decompose the N-channel EEG signal into N temporally independent components (ICs) from different brain (and non-brain) sources (Makeig et al., 1996). This separation and identification of independent brain sources is essential to characterize the neuropsychological origins of the brain processes, and to relate a specific task with the activity and topography of those brain sources (Jung et al., 2001). We employed the runica extended mode training parameters (Lee et al., 1999), and a stopping weight change set to $1e - 7$. The runica extension allows to separate out a wider range of source signals (super- and sub-Gaussian), while the selected stopping criterion lengthens ICA training. This makes it possible to obtain cleaner and reliable components, especially with the limited number of epochs in haptic studies. After completing ICA training and decomposition, non-brain and artifactual components were discarded by visual inspection of their scalp topography and power spectra (Makeig et al., 1997).

The topography of the remaining independent components (IC) was then analyzed using DIPFIT2, a plug-in for EEGLAB (Oostenveld & Oostendorp, 2002). This tool localizes equivalent dipole sources in a three-dimensional space (x, y, z), based on the location and activity of the scalp electrodes (we used a boundary element model of the head). ICs were then clustered using the STUDY function of EEGLAB. First, we selected only ICs that contained less than 30% residual variance and were located inside the brain (139 clusters selected, approximately 8 clusters per participant). The clustering procedure was based on dipole location, scalp topography, spectral power and event-related spectral perturbation (ERSP), and was performed as follows: 1) scalp

1 topography, spectral power and ERSP were pre-computed; 2) all the measures except
2 dipole location were compressed into a 10-dimensional vector using principal
3 component analysis (PCA); 3) dipole location was combined into a 3-dimensional
4 vector (corresponding to the x, y and z coordinates), resulting in 33-dimensional
5 combined measure space; 4) we normalized all the measures by dividing the measure
6 data of all PCAs by the standard deviation of the first principal component in the
7 specific measure. Before entering clustering, measures were weighted according to the
8 desired magnitude of their individual contribution to the cluster process. Dipole
9 locations were weighted by a factor of 10, ERSP and spectral power by a factor of 3,
10 and scalp topography by a factor of 5. Finally, we applied the EEGLAB k-means
11 algorithm to the combined measures to produce 8 maximally distinct clusters
12 (independent components with locations more than 3 standard deviations away from the
13 cluster centroid were removed from the resulting cluster). We analyzed only those
14 component clusters located over sensorimotor, parietal and frontal regions that showed
15 relevant ERSP modulations in alpha and beta bands during the task period. Therefore,
16 the IC clusters obtained were selected to enter the posterior analyses according to the
17 visual inspection of their topographies, the spectral activity, and the Talairach
18 coordinates of the cluster centroid coordinates.

19 2.2.3. Time/frequency analysis of event-related spectral perturbations (ERSP)

20 Event-related spectral changes in power spectrum (ERSP) for each IC cluster were
21 computed over the entire epoch length in each experimental condition (Makeig, 1993).
22 To avoid the inclusion of the brain activity arising from the verbal instruction that
23 signaled the start of the trial, we employed the pre-stimulus interval -1000/ -300 ms as
24 the baseline period. To estimate ERSP, we computed the power spectrum over a sliding
25 latency window in each frequency band. Next, we calculated the average across trials

1 and plotted the results as changes in spectral log amplitude relative to the baseline.
2 Time-frequency analysis was performed using Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) with
3 Hanning window tapering (Delorme & Makeig, 2004). This method provides time-
4 varying estimates of the magnitude of the signal in each frequency band with a good
5 balance between time and frequency resolution (Martinovic, Lawson, & Craddock,
6 2012). All the time frequency analyses were carried out using EEGLAB functions along
7 with custom scripts.

8 To deal with the multiple comparison problem arising from the multidimensionality
9 and spatiotemporal structure of the electrophysiological data (Frehlich et al., 2016), we
10 performed statistical analyses on the ERSP of the selected IC clusters using the Fieldtrip
11 plug-in for MATLAB (Oostenveld, Fries, Maris, & Schoffelen, 2011) and the non-
12 parametric cluster-based permutation/Monte Carlo statistics to determine the significant
13 differences between experimental conditions. Time/frequency characteristics of all
14 component epochs were first split into x samples corresponding to the experimental
15 conditions; the difference in means between these x samples was then calculated (the
16 observed value T). Next, particular values were divided into groups of size n_x in every
17 possible way (every permutation of the groups), and difference in sample means was
18 calculated for each permutation to obtain the distribution of possible differences under
19 the null hypothesis that the group label does not matter. Finally, p -values were
20 calculated as the proportion of sampled permutations where the difference in means was
21 greater than or equal to T . Post-hoc paired t-tests of related samples were performed
22 where necessary.

23 2.3. Results

24 2.3.1. Behavioral results

1 Because of the randomized position of the target pairs, response times depended
2 heavily on target position and scanning speed. To ensure that the scanning speed was
3 the same across all conditions, we linearly regressed the data and fitted a regression line
4 to compare the intercepts and slopes of each condition (Overvliet et al., 2012). A one-
5 way repeated measures ANOVA showed no statistical differences between conditions in
6 the intercepts or in the search slopes (all $ps > 0.05$), ensuring that any possible
7 difference in response times were attributable to grouping manipulations and not to
8 different scanning speeds or to different amounts of time to start moving the hand.

9 The 2-way repeated measures ANOVA conducted on the RTs yielded a main effect
10 of target position [$F(2, 19) = 122.19; p < 0.001; \eta^2p = 0.859$], indicating that RTs
11 increased as a function of target position. Pairwise comparisons showed significant
12 differences between all target positions (all $ps < 0.001$). The main effect of grouping
13 condition was also significant [$F(2, 19) = 20.459; p < 0.001; \eta^2p = 0.506$]. Pairwise
14 comparisons showed that the mean RT for the single condition was faster than the other
15 conditions. Also, the mean RT for the cooperative condition was faster than for the
16 competitive condition. No other effects or interactions reached statistical significance.
17 The data from the raw RT analysis is plotted in Figure 3-left and Table 1 top row.

2 **Fig. 3.** Left: Mean RTs (ms) for the three grouping conditions when the 3 relative target
3 positions were collapsed. Right: Mean RT (ms) for the three grouping conditions
4 corrected for the absolute target position (the bars represent ± 1 SE).

5

6 Even though the relative position (in terms of number of elements) of the targets in
7 the three conditions was the same (3/4, 4/5, 5/6; see Figure 2), the absolute position (in
8 terms of distance from the beginning of the pattern) of a given target differed across the
9 grouping conditions (e.g., if the target position was 3/4, the absolute distance from the
10 stimulus start in the cooperative condition was greater than in the other two conditions
11 due to the gap between the previous element and the target pair). To account for this
12 difference in the target pairs across grouping conditions, we reduced the target positions
13 to those that were comparable in terms of absolute distance, obtaining two absolute
14 target positions (4/5, 5/6) corresponding to relative positions 3/4 and 4/5 in the
15 cooperative condition, 4/5 and 5/6 in the competitive condition, and 4/5 and 5/6 in the
16 neutral condition. Next, we conducted a 2 absolute target position x 3 grouping
17 condition repeated measures ANOVA on the RTs. As could be expected, the results
18 showed a main effect of absolute target position [$F(1, 11) = 4.27; p = 0.001; \eta^2 p =$

1 0.624], indicating an increase in RT as a function of the distance between the target and
 2 the beginning of the haptic pattern. More interesting, the main effect of grouping
 3 condition also reached statistical significance [$F(1, 11) = 4.27; p = 0.001; \eta^2 p =$
 4 0.624]. *Post-hoc* pair-wise comparisons showed differences in RTs between all
 5 grouping conditions, with faster RTs in the cooperative condition followed by the single
 6 and competitive conditions (see Figure 3-right and Table 1 bottom row).

7 **Table 1.** Experiment 1 mean response times as a function of grouping condition, for
 8 both relative and absolute target positions

Target position	Grouping condition				
	Single	Coop.	Comp.	Fac.	Interf.
Relative	2995 (483)	3077 (472)	3195 (518)	82 (126)	200 (154)
Absolute	3256 (551)	2812 (411)	3456 (597)	-444 (184)	200 (202)

9 Single: similarity only condition; Coop.: cooperative condition; Comp.: competitive
 10 condition; Fac.: Coop. RTs – Single RTs; Interf.: Comp. RTs – Single RTs

11

12 A 2-way repeated measures ANOVA conducted on accuracy (error rates) showed
 13 that neither the main effects nor the interaction reached statistical significance (all p s >
 14 0.05). The mean accuracy of the task was 94%.

15 2.3.2. EEG results: IC-cluster Event-Related Spectral Perturbations

16 After pre-processing the EEG data, the remaining ICs (139) were grouped into 8
 17 clusters according to their dipole locations, scalp maps, spectral power and ERSP
 18 activity (weighted by a factor of 10, 5, 1 and 3 respectively). In addition, and given that
 19 no significant interaction between grouping conditions and target position was found,
 20 we collapsed the data from all the different target positions to increase the statistical
 21 power. Two participants were removed from the EEG analyses due to the noisy data.
 22 Thus, all the EEG analyses were conducted on the remaining 19 participants. Five
 23 clusters were selected to enter the statistical analyses following the criteria specified in
 24 section 2.2.2: Left and right sensorimotor, right prefrontal, right parietal and left

- 1 occipital. The scalp maps, dipole source localizations and power spectra of the selected
- 2 IC clusters are plotted in Figure 4.

3
 4 **Figure 4.** Average scalp maps, dipole source location in average brain images (the red
 5 dot represents the cluster centroid), Talairach coordinates and power spectra of 5 IC
 6 clusters from 19 subjects. (A) Left sensorimotor (n=14); (B) right sensorimotor (n=16);
 7 (C) right pre-frontal (n=25); (D) left occipital (n=14) and (E) right parietal (n=16).

- 1 To analyze differences in oscillatory brain activity between grouping conditions,
- 2 ERSPs were computed and plotted under all experimental conditions along with
- 3 significant differences between them (see Figure 5).

1
2 **Figure 5.** Average event-related spectral perturbations (ERSP) of the five IC clusters
3 selected for further analysis in the three grouping conditions of Experiment 1. From top
4 to bottom: left sensorimotor, right sensorimotor, right prefrontal, left occipital and right
5 parietal.

1 Figure 5c shows the oscillatory brain activity of a right prefrontal IC cluster
2 (Brodmann area 10, right dorsolateral pre-frontal cortex). The analysis of the ERSP
3 showed significant differences in alpha-band (10-12 Hz) event-related
4 desynchronization (ERD) between conditions. Post-hoc comparisons showed that this
5 ERD was significantly more pronounced in the competitive condition compared with
6 the cooperative condition throughout the first 2000 ms of the epoch. Additionally, we
7 found beta-band ERD around 20 Hz. Post-hoc comparisons indicated that it was more
8 pronounced during the first 2000 ms of the competitive condition than in the other
9 grouping conditions.

10 ERSP from a right parietal IC cluster (Brodmann area 7, somatosensory association
11 cortex) is plotted in Figure 5e. ERSP analyses showed significant alpha (10-12 Hz) and
12 beta (15-25 Hz) band ERD differences between grouping conditions. *Post-hoc*
13 comparisons indicated that this ERD was more pronounced in the competition condition
14 relative to cooperative condition throughout the 1500-3500 ms interval.

15 Finally, Figures 5a, 5b and 5d display the ERSP of the left sensorimotor (Brodmann
16 areas 4-6, motor and premotor cortex), right sensorimotor (Brodmann areas 1-2-3,
17 primary somatosensory cortex) and left occipital (Brodmann area 19, associative visual
18 cortex) IC clusters respectively. All three IC clusters showed a marked alpha-band (10-
19 12 Hz) ERD that began within the first 500 ms of the epoch, peaked in the interval
20 between 1500-2000 ms, and started to re-synchronize within the last 1000 ms of the
21 epoch. Beta-band ERD (18-20 Hz) was also evident in all three IC clusters, especially in
22 the left sensorimotor one (see Figure 5a), but its duration and intensity was lower than
23 the alpha-band desynchronization. Notably, in the clusters and conditions in which the
24 beta band was more pronounced, beta-band ERD began about 500 ms after the onset of
25 the haptic exploration and started to resynchronize after the first 2000 ms of the epoch.

1 No statistically significant differences between grouping conditions appeared in any of
2 the three IC clusters (left and right sensorimotor, left occipital).

3 **3. Experiment 2**

4 The results of Experiment 1 indicate that the conjoined effect of proximity grouping
5 exerts an influence on performance of a task in which target discrimination depends on
6 grouping by texture similarity. Specifically, the task was facilitated when proximity
7 grouped the haptic pattern in the same way as texture similarity (cooperation condition),
8 while performance was hindered when proximity grouped the pattern in opposite
9 different way (competitive condition). The ICA analysis and IC clustering also revealed
10 the activation of a widespread network of bilateral sensorimotor areas, along with right
11 parietal, right prefrontal and left occipital cortices. In addition, the ERSP analysis
12 showed greater activation in both the pre-frontal and parietal clusters, as reflected by the
13 stronger alpha- and beta-band ERD in the competition condition. In Experiment 2, we
14 examined the influence of grouping by texture similarity in a task in which targets were
15 defined by means of spatial proximity grouping. Here, we employed a variant of the
16 discrimination task in which participants were presented with a row of 6 to 8 elements
17 that formed two different cohorts (left/right) based on their spatial proximity.
18 Participants had to indicate which side of the haptic display (cohorts grouped by spatial
19 proximity) had more elements, or not respond if the number of elements was the same
20 (catch trials). In this case, texture similarity facilitates (cooperation condition) or
21 hinders (competition condition) the proximity-based task.

22 **3.1. Method**

23 **3.1.1. Participants**

1 A new group of 23 students (6 males; age range: 19-50, mean age = 30.55, SD =
2 7.73) from the Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia (UNED) participated in
3 Experiment 2. All of them reported being right-handed, had normal tactile perception
4 and were naïve to the purpose of the experiment. Before the start of the experiment they
5 completed the same handedness inventory and informed consent form as in Experiment
6 1.

7 3.1.2. Apparatus and stimuli

8 The device and the haptic stimuli were the same as in Experiment 1. The stimuli
9 were arranged in a row of 6 to 8 elements with three different configurations: (1) In the
10 cooperative condition, each cohort was defined by spatial proximity (6 mm within
11 cohorts; 24 mm between cohorts), and all its elements had the same texture, but the
12 texture of each cohort was different; (2) In the competitive condition, all the cylinders
13 of the cohort with the largest number of elements had the same texture, except the last
14 one (the nearest to the opposite cohort), which had the same texture as the opposite
15 cohort; (3) Finally, single (proximity acting alone) stimuli were those in which the
16 texture of the two cohorts alternated, without any explicit texture similarity grouping.
17 Figure 6 shows a list of the different displays used in Experiment 2.

1. Proximity only (single)

2. Combined grouping principles (Cooperation)

3. Combined grouping principles (Competition)

1

2 **Fig. 6.** Representation of all the experimental conditions used in Experiment 2: (1)
3 proximity acting alone, (2) cooperation between grouping principles, and (3)
4 competition between grouping principles. The bottom two rows of each condition
5 represent the catch trials.

6

7 3.1.3. Design and procedure

8 We employed a unifactorial within-subjects design with 3 grouping conditions
9 (cooperative, competitive, neutral). As in Experiment 1, the dependent variables were
10 RT and accuracy. Participants indicated as fast and as accurately as possible which of
11 the two cohorts had the most elements. Participants explored the row of elements
12 sequentially with the index and middle fingers of the right hand, and responded by
13 pressing one of two foot pedals (one for the “left” and the other for the “right” cohort).

1 In addition, to avoid the possibility of identifying the largest cohort without exploring
2 the whole haptic pattern, catch trials were added, in which the number of elements was
3 the same in both cohorts; for these trials, participants were instructed to make no
4 response (see Figure 6). The total number of trials (120: 96 + 24 catch trials) was
5 conducted in a single block lasting approximately 40-50 minutes. The rest of the
6 procedure was the same as the one described in Experiment 1 (see paragraph 2.1.3).

7 3.1.4. EEG acquisition and pre-processing

8 EEG acquisition and offline pre-processing followed the same procedure as in
9 Experiment 1 (see paragraph 2.1.4). The mean number of artifact-free epochs per
10 participant was 71 (Min/Max: 55-79).

11 3.2. Data analysis

12 3.2.1. Behavioral data

13 We conducted two separate unifactorial repeated measures ANOVAs with 3
14 grouping conditions (cooperative, competitive, single) on RTs from trials followed by
15 correct responses (16.66% of trials rejected) and accuracy (error rates). All the statistical
16 tests were Bonferroni corrected.

17 In addition, to compare the results of both experiments we performed two new 3 x 2
18 mixed ANOVAs on RTs and accuracy with grouping condition as the within subjects
19 factor and experiment as the between subject factor.

20 Last, to examine the compatibility of the data from both Experiments with an
21 additive account of the interactive effects of grouping cues, we transformed the RT data
22 to obtain normalized effect sizes, employing the method originally developed by
23 Kubovy and van den Berg (2008) in vision, and previously employed by Prieto et al.
24 (2018b) to account for the combined grouping effects in phenomenological and

1 psychophysical tasks in touch. To this end, we first computed a differential variable I by
2 transforming the raw RTs as follows: $I = \text{single condition} - \text{conjoined condition}$
3 (competitive or cooperative). Positive scores indicate the facilitation (ms) of the non-
4 relevant grouping cue, whereas negative scores indicate the interference of the non-
5 relevant cue. The differential scores of Experiments 1 and 2 are summarized in Tables 1
6 and 2 respectively. After that, I was normalized using the effect size D ($D = I/\text{Standard}$
7 $\text{error of } I$). The D values were then adjusted to fall between the -1/+1 interval by
8 assuming the highest D value as 1 (or -1) in the normalized scale and computing the
9 remaining normalized effect sizes as the ratio between the observed D and the highest D
10 ($D / \text{highest } D \text{ value observed}$). The 0 value represents the scores for single conditions.

11 *3.2.2. Independent component analysis (ICA) and component clustering*

12 ICA analysis and component clustering followed the same procedure as in
13 Experiment 1 (see paragraph 2.2.2)

14 *3.2.3. Time/frequency analysis of event-related spectral perturbations (ERSP)*

15 As in Experiment 1, event-related spectral changes in power spectrum (ERSP) for
16 each IC cluster were computed over the entire epoch length (-1000 – 4000 ms) in each
17 experimental condition (Makeig, 1993). The details of ERSP computing were the same
18 as in Experiment 1 (see paragraph 2.2.3).

19 Statistical analyses of EEG recordings were conducted following the same
20 guidelines outlined for Experiment 1 (see paragraph 2.2.4).

21

22

23

1 3.3. Results

2 3.3.1. Behavioral results

3 Behavioral data from Experiment 2 were analyzed using a unifactorial repeated
4 measures ANOVA on both response times and task accuracy (the main results are
5 summarized in Figure 7 and Table 2).

7 **Fig. 7.** Left: Mean RT (ms) for the three different grouping conditions. Right: Mean
8 error rates (%) for the three grouping conditions (the bars represent ± 1 SE).

9

10 **Table 2.** Experiment 2. Mean response times as a function of grouping condition.

Grouping condition				
Single	Coop.	Comp.	Fac.	Interf.
2458 (579)	2413 (592)	2451 (643)	-46 (112)	-7 (135)

11

12 The results of the ANOVA performed on RT data showed no significant effects of
13 grouping condition (all $ps > 0.05$). The ANOVA conducted on accuracy (error rates)
14 showed that the main effect of grouping was significant [$F(2, 21) = 7.22; p = 0.004;$
15 $\eta^2p = 0.407$]. Pairwise comparisons indicated that the number of errors in the
16 competitive condition was greater than in the cooperative condition ($p = 0.003$). No
17 other effects reached statistical significance (all $ps > 0.05$).

3.3.2. Cross-experiment analysis and compatibility with additivity of grouping effects

The results of the cross-experiment ANOVA performed on RT data showed a significant main effect of experiment [$F(1, 42) = 15.35; p < 0.001; \eta^2p = 0.268$], indicating slower RTs in Experiment 1 relative to Experiment 2. The grouping x experiment interaction was also significant [$F(1, 42) = 41.43; p < 0.001; \eta^2p = 0.497$]. Post-hoc comparisons indicated that significant differences between grouping conditions were restricted to Experiment 1 (see Experiment 1 ANOVA for details). The results of the ANOVA performed on error rates showed the main effect of experiment reached statistical significance [$F(2, 41) = 12.43; p < 0.001; \eta^2p = 0.228$], indicating that the error rate was greater in Experiment 2. More interesting, the grouping x experiment interaction was also significant [$F(1, 42) = 41.43; p < 0.001; \eta^2p = 0.497$]. Post-hoc comparisons indicated that significant differences between grouping conditions were restricted to the cooperation and competition conditions of Experiment 2 (see Experiment 2 ANOVA for details).

Last, the results obtained from the normalization of the effect sizes in Experiments 1 and 2 showed that both cooperative conditions fall above the single condition, indicating larger facilitation effects when proximity was the non-relevant cue (Experiment 1). In the competitive conditions, the normalized size effects were below the single condition and were only evident when proximity was the non-relevant cue. This result suggests that interference effects only appeared in Experiment 1, when proximity was the interfering cue. The normalized effect sizes are summarized in Figure 8 and the inferences about additivity are listed in Table 3.

1 **Fig. 8.** Normalized effect sizes used to examine the additivity of the data from
 2 Experiment 2. Cooperation between principles is identified by (◯) and competition by
 3 (÷). The grouping cue on the left is the task-relevant one, and the one on the right non-
 4 relevant (interfering). Positive scores indicate facilitation and negative scores
 5 interference.
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1 **Table 3.** Inferences about the compatibility of the data from Experiments 1 and 2
 2 with additivity effects of grouping

Data	Inference	Relation to additivity		
		Compatible	Not incompatible	Incompatible
$D(s \circ p) > D(s)$	The O combination of s and p is stronger than s	✓		
$D(p \circ s) > D(p)$	The O combination of p and s is stronger than p	✓		
$D(s \div p) < D(s)$	The \div combination of p and s is not stronger than p	✓		
$D(p \div s) < D(p)$	The \div combination of p and s is not stronger than s		✓	
$D(p \circ s) > D(p \div s)$	The O combination of p and s is stronger than the \div combination of p and s	✓		
$D(s \circ p) > D(s \div p)$	The O combination of s and p is stronger than the \div combination of s and p	✓		
$D(p \circ s) > D(p) > D(p \div s)$	The O combination of p and s is stronger than p and the \div combination of p and s		✓	
$D(s \circ p) > D(s) > D(s \div p)$	The O combination of s and p is stronger than s and the \div combination of s and p	✓		

3 D represents the normalized measure of effect sizes; p , proximity; s , similarity; \circ ,
 4 cooperation; \div , competition. The first grouping cue within parentheses is the task-
 5 relevant cue, and the second is the non-relevant (interfering) one.

6

7 3.3.3. EEG results: IC-cluster Event-Related Spectral Perturbations

8 After the pre-processing of the EEG data, the 169 remaining ICs in Experiment 2
 9 were grouped into 8 clusters according to their dipole locations, scalp maps, spectral
 10 power and ERSP activity. One participant was removed from the EEG analyses due to
 11 the noisy EEG data, so all the EEG analyses were conducted on the remaining 22
 12 participants. According to the criteria established, statistical analysis was conducted on
 13 five IC clusters, whose overall locations were similar to those found in Experiment 1:

- 1 left and right sensorimotor, right prefrontal, right parietal and left occipital. The features
- 2 of the selected IC clusters are plotted in Figure 9.

3

1 **Figure 9.** Average scalp maps, dipole source location in average brain images (the red
2 dot represents the cluster centroid), Talairach coordinates and power spectra of 5 IC
3 clusters from 22 subjects in Experiment 2. (A) Left sensorimotor (n=18); (B) right
4 sensorimotor (n=18); (C) right pre-frontal (n=17); (D) left occipital (n=28); (E) right
5 parietal (n=35).

6
7 Figures 10a and 10b show the ERSPs of left (Brodmann areas 4-6, right primary
8 motor and pre-motor cortices) and right (Brodmann area 40, supramarginal gyrus)
9 sensorimotor IC clusters. Both clusters showed a strong alpha-band ERD, especially in
10 the 10-12 Hz range. The alpha ERD began immediately after the onset of the haptic
11 exploration in both clusters, but in the left sensorimotor cluster the resynchronization of
12 the alpha band started earlier (around 3000 ms) than in the right sensorimotor cluster, in
13 which alpha-band ERD seemed to last throughout the entire epoch. Beta-band ERD (18-
14 22 Hz) was also evident in both IC clusters, but its duration and intensity was lower
15 than the alpha-band ERD. In addition, beta-band activity in the left sensorimotor cluster
16 showed an event-related synchronization (ERS) following the ERD in the last 1000 ms
17 of the epoch. No statistically significant differences between conditions arose in either
18 IC cluster.

1
2 **Figure 10.** Average event-related spectral perturbations (ERSP) of the five IC clusters
3 selected for further analysis in the three grouping conditions of Experiment 2. From top
4 to bottom: left sensorimotor, right sensorimotor, right prefrontal, left occipital and right
5 parietal.

1
2 The results of the event related spectral activity from the right frontal (Brodmann
3 area 10, right dorsolateral pre-frontal cortex) and right parietal (Brodmann area 7,
4 somatosensory association cortex) IC clusters are plotted in Figures 10c and 10e,
5 respectively. The two clusters showed a similar alpha-band ERD from the beginning of
6 the task period, centered in the 10-12 Hz range and peaking around 1500 ms. The alpha
7 band started to resynchronize approximately in the 2000-2500 ms time window. Beta-
8 band activity followed a similar pattern in the two clusters, with an intensity peak that
9 coincided with the intensity peak of the alpha band. No statistical differences were
10 found between conditions.

11 Finally, Figure 10d shows the ERSP activity of the left occipital IC cluster found in
12 Experiment 2 (Brodmann area 19, associative visual cortex). As in the previous IC
13 clusters, there was a strong alpha-band ERD centered around 10 Hz that peaked around
14 1500 ms and resynchronized about 2000 ms after the start of the task period. Beta-band
15 ERD, on the other hand, was located in the 20-22 Hz range and peaked at the same time
16 as the alpha-band ERD. No significant differences were found between grouping
17 conditions.

18 **4. General discussion**

19 The aim of the current study was to examine the interaction effects and dominance
20 dynamics between grouping principles in touch, along with their neural correlates. This
21 work was motivated by the scarcity of research addressing the topic in the haptic
22 modality. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to investigate the brain
23 activity that underlies the interactions in the perceptual grouping processes when
24 grouping cues act conjoined in the haptic modality.

1 Four main conclusions can be drawn from this haptic study: (1) proximity
2 dominated the perceptual grouping process when it acted conjoined with texture
3 similarity; (2) the results are compatible with the additivity of the conjoined grouping
4 effects; (3) ICA revealed the involvement of a widespread network of ipsi- and contra-
5 lateral sensorimotor, ipsilateral (right) prefrontal and parietal, and contralateral (left)
6 occipital brain areas in both experiments; and (4) ERSP analyses indicated a greater
7 activation of right dorsolateral pre-frontal and parietal IC clusters in the competitive
8 condition in Experiment 1. This is in agreement with the behavioral dominance and
9 more intense interference of proximity over similarity cues in our previous research on
10 the topic. These results and their implications are discussed in the following sections.

11 4.1. Dominance dynamics and additive effects of interactions between grouping 12 principles in touch

13 In Experiment 1, participants responded faster when the grouping cues cooperated
14 to group the stimuli in the same way. By contrast, RTs were slower when the two
15 grouping cues competed so that proximity tended to group the target with the
16 distractors. On the other hand, in Experiment 2 the non-relevant cue (texture similarity)
17 did not affect RTs in either the competitive or the cooperative condition, although
18 participants made more errors when the two principles where conjoined in competition.
19 In addition, comparison of the overall RTs between experiments indicates that
20 participants responded faster when targets were grouped by proximity (Experiment 2)
21 than by similarity (Experiment 1). Finally, the analysis of the normalized effect sizes
22 supports the RT and accuracy data. The effect sizes of the conjoined conditions
23 (competition and cooperation) were much larger when the non-relevant cue was
24 proximity (Experiment 1) than when it was texture similarity (Experiment 2). Thus, this
25 pattern of results supports our hypothesis regarding the dominance of proximity

1 grouping when the two principles act together, because: (1) participants' responses were
2 faster and more accurate when targets were grouped by proximity; (2) proximity
3 grouping was less interfered by the competitive presence of texture similarity; and (3)
4 responses to similarity grouped targets were facilitated by the cooperative presence of
5 proximity cues, but not vice versa. Importantly, the dominance of proximity grouping
6 occurred even though the phenomenological strength of the two grouping cues was
7 equated.

8 Our haptic results agree with previous findings in vision using phenomenological
9 and psychophysical tasks (Luna et al, 2016; Palmer & Beck, 2007), and with our
10 previous findings obtained in touch employing phenomenological and directed-attention
11 psychophysical task (see Prieto et al., 2018b). In those studies, phenomenological
12 ratings of grouping effects were higher for conjoined cooperative conditions, followed
13 by acting alone and competitive conditions respectively. In addition, responses to
14 psychophysical tasks were slowed down by the non-attended/non-relevant grouping
15 cues when grouping principles were conjoined in competition and speeded up when the
16 two principles cooperated, compared to the condition when one principle acted alone.
17 Interestingly, the specific cues that dominate the perceptual scene seem to differ
18 between modalities. Specifically, Quinlan and Wilton (1998) found no dominance of
19 proximity when it was pitted against color and shape similarity (see also, Luna et al.,
20 2016) but Prieto et al. (2018b) found a clear dominance of proximity grouping using the
21 same tasks.

22 At least other two studies have compared these two grouping principles in touch.
23 First, Chang et al. (2007b) investigated whether people grouped visual and haptic
24 displays in the same manner when proximity and color/texture similarity were used as
25 grouping cues. Their results indicate that when an unequal distance was perceived

1 between the individual elements, the participants tended to group them using spatial
2 proximity rather than texture similarity, a finding that also matches the proximity
3 dominance found in the present study. Furthermore, a previous study (Prieto et al.,
4 2014) showed faster and more accurate responses to proximity-grouped stimuli in a
5 speeded haptic task in which participants had to detect the orientation of haptic patterns
6 formed by either proximity or texture similarity.

7 Finally, we found that most of our data (except in the competition condition, Exp.2)
8 fall into an impressively regular pattern, in which the single (acting alone) grouping
9 principles fall between the two conjoining (competitive/cooperative) conditions as
10 shown in vision (Kubovy & van den Berg, 2008). This overall pattern allows us to infer
11 that the interaction effects between proximity and texture similarity in touch are, at
12 least, compatible with an additive account of grouping effects. However, these results
13 cannot be taken as definitive, as different tasks, grouping cues, and combinations of
14 grouping strengths need to be considered and compared using more precise formal
15 models before we can draw solid and generalizable conclusions on the additivity of
16 perceptual grouping in touch.

17 4.2. Independent Component Analysis (ICA) and Event-Related Spectral Perturbations 18 (ERSP)

19 The transient ERSP in alpha and beta spectral power of ICA-decomposed EEGs
20 shows that the two experiments involved activation of similar brain areas, as revealed
21 by the spectral activity of the clusters obtained after ICA decomposition, and the
22 localization of the equivalent dipoles of each cluster (Figures 4 and 9). According to the
23 hypotheses of the study, these areas include left and right sensorimotor μ clusters. The
24 bilateral localization around the central sulcus, spreading across the motor, pre-motor
25 and somatosensory cortices is consistent with the commonly reported sources of this

1 rhythm (Pineda, 2005) and its implication in haptic tasks (Lin, Shaw, Young, Lin, &
2 Jung, 2012). The brain areas involved also include right parietal and pre-frontal IC
3 clusters. The first area has been related to diverse functions in haptic perception such as:
4 goal-directed finger movements in object exploration (Binkofski et al., 1999), length
5 discrimination (Bodegård, Geyer, Grefkes, Zilles, & Roland, 2001), and shape
6 representation (Reed, Caselli, & Farah, 1996). The right pre-frontal cortex, on the other
7 hand, has been associated with a great number of high order and executive functions,
8 including: encoding of non-verbal material (Kelley et al., 1998), active maintenance of
9 somatosensory information (Fletcher & Henson, 2001), response selection (Rowe, Toni,
10 Josephs, Frackowiak, & Passingham, 2000), and the organization of the entire process
11 (exploration-discrimination-response selection) of the task (Stoeckel et al., 2003). More
12 interestingly, the conjoined activation of frontal (including pre-motor) and parietal areas
13 is thought to be implicated in the processing and short-term storage and discrimination
14 of stimuli (Stoeckel et al., 2003). Finally, the activity of the left occipital IC cluster
15 found in both experiments might indicate the activation of visual areas. This
16 contribution of visual areas has been reported in other haptic studies, especially in
17 object recognition (Sathian, 2005). As the active sites found in IC-cluster analysis are
18 known to play an important role in haptic perception, the findings support the detailed
19 analysis of the activity within these clusters. In the following sections we will discuss
20 each of them in turn.

21 4.2.1. Left and right sensorimotor clusters

22 The present study suggest the engagement of left ipsi- and contra-lateral
23 sensorimotor IC clusters in a haptic exploration task evidenced by the alpha- (10-12 Hz)
24 and beta- (18-22 Hz) band event-related desynchronization (ERD) in both IC clusters.
25 Given that alpha-band desynchronization has been linked to high excitability and

1 increased brain activity (Klimesch et al., 2007), this alpha ERD may be related to
2 movement organization, voluntary hand and finger movements during the task (primary
3 motor cortex), somatosensory perception, finger proprioception, and localization of
4 touch (primary somatosensory cortex). This is in accordance with earlier studies that
5 found similar activity of primary sensorimotor cortex (M1, S1), supplementary (SMA)
6 and pre- motor areas (PMA) during grouping tasks in touch modality (Prieto et al.
7 2018a). A similar but less pronounced ERD/ERS pattern was explicit in the beta
8 band. The desynchronization of beta rhythms within the sensorimotor cortex in response
9 to external stimuli has usually been related to sensory processing, motor learning and
10 motor skills (Sochůrková, Rektor, Jurák, & Stančák, 2006). In particular, Lin et al.
11 (2012), using a visuomotor tracking task, found stronger beta-band suppression in
12 epochs with haptic feedback due to the increased sensory processing and motor
13 demands, in a contralateral sensorimotor IC cluster of similar characteristics and
14 localization as the one found in our study. Taken together, the results agree with
15 previous studies that linked the increased bilateral activity in sensory and motor areas
16 with the performance of voluntary movements, and the acquisition and processing of
17 tactile information through the fingertips. Finally, the lack of significant differences
18 between grouping conditions in Experiments 1 and 2 was also expected, given that the
19 haptic exploratory activity and the sensory processing demands were almost identical in
20 the different experimental conditions.

21 4.2.2. Right parietal and pre-frontal clusters

22 The analysis of the oscillatory brain activity (Experiments 1 and 2) revealed the
23 activation of right (ipsilateral) parietal and pre-frontal IC clusters. The increased activity
24 within the right parietal cortex has been associated with several different cognitive
25 processes, particularly in the spatial domain like: the integration of spatial information

1 and sensorimotor behavior, especially when the movements are guided by external
2 haptic feedback (Classen et al., 1998); the discrimination of the macro (shape and
3 length) and micro-geometric (rough) properties of the tactile objects, in the anterior
4 intraparietal sulcus (IPA) and the lateral parietal operculum (LPO), respectively
5 (Roland, O'Sullivan & Kawashima 1998); attention and short-term storage of
6 somatosensory information, particularly in the context of its association with the pre-
7 frontal cortex (Smith & Jonides, 1997); and the manipulation of non-verbal information
8 during working memory tasks (Rowe et al., 2000). Particularly, the strong connections
9 between the parietal and the prefrontal cortex would be responsible for the transfer from
10 unimodal specific areas to the areas where information is manipulated and updated
11 online (Petrides & Pandya, 1984). Interestingly, this fronto-parietal circuit also seems to
12 play a crucial role in tactile object discrimination (Stoeckel et al., 2003). Taking this
13 evidence into account, the engagement of the right parietal and prefrontal areas in both
14 Experiments might be related to the need to integrate the micro- (roughness) and macro-
15 geometric (spatial proximity and total length) features of the haptic patterns into a
16 unified percept. According to this view, the conjoined activity of the parietal and
17 prefrontal cortex would be necessary to integrate or group the disjointed information of
18 each individual item, to maintain this information in working memory, and to
19 update/manipulate it as the haptic exploration continues. The integrated/grouped
20 information would then be used to discriminate between the different possible stimulus
21 configurations and make a decision about the appropriate response according to the task
22 goals. This could also explain the more intense ERD in alpha and beta bands in the
23 competitive condition in Experiment 1. The enhanced brain activity would result from
24 the greater cognitive demands in the grouping process when participants tried to
25 integrate incongruent cues into a coherent and stable percept. The fact that both clusters

1 showed significant differences between conditions in sequential time windows suggests
2 the joint action of the two areas within a parieto-frontal integrated circuit of tactile
3 discrimination (Stoeckel et al., 2003).

4 4.2.3. Left occipital cluster

5 . In both experiments, analysis of the ERSP shows a clear ERD extended over all
6 the task period in the alpha and beta-bands. There is strong evidence suggesting that
7 tactile perception evokes activity within visual cortical areas, particularly the parieto-
8 occipital region (POC) and lateral occipital complex (LOC). Several studies reported
9 this evidence in a number of different tasks and cognitive processes, including tactile
10 discrimination of grating orientation (Zhang et al., 2005), perception of two-
11 dimensional patterns and three-dimensional objects (Prather, Votaw, & Sathian, 2004),
12 shape processing (Snow, Strother, & Humphreys, 2014), and object recognition
13 (Strother, Zhou, Vilis, & Snow, 2016). Interestingly, two different studies have found
14 increased activity within the left lateral occipital complex (LOC) in tasks that require
15 either the tactile discrimination of the orientation of gratings (Zangaladze, Epstein,
16 Grafton, & Sathian, 1999) or the tactile discrimination of macrospatial features of the
17 stimuli (Stoesz et al., 2003). By contrast, they did not find any activity within the LOC
18 when the tasks involved the detection of microspatial features (detecting a gap) or
19 texture discrimination. Given that our tasks relied specifically on texture and gap
20 (proximity) features, our findings of the engagement of the occipital cortex, especially
21 in extra-striate areas that overlap with the areas included in the LOC (Grill-Spector,
22 Kourtzi, & Kanwisher, 2001), are somewhat surprising especially given that previous
23 results in the haptic modality (Prieto et al. 2018a) found no significant activation of
24 occipital areas. One possible explanation is that discrimination between textures and/or
25 different spatial proximities was not the primary goal of our grouping tasks (as

1 previously mentioned). Our participants performed indirect tasks in which they were not
2 aware of the relevance of the grouping cues. Consequently, the engagement of visual
3 areas could result from the need to form a representation of the haptic stimulus after the
4 integration of low-level features. In fact, some studies have emphasized the role of
5 visual imagery in the haptic perception of orientation, shape and size (Zangaladze et al.,
6 1999). In addition, Strother et al. (2016) found that activation of visual areas was
7 contralateral to the hand used and not dependent on the side of the presentation, which
8 is in line with the left occipital activity obtained in the present study. Another possible
9 explanation is that activity in visual areas does not reflect the conversion of the haptic
10 information into visual imagery, but some kind of multisensory representation of
11 information. This possibility has already been contemplated in studies that found
12 different occipital activation patterns for spatial and non-spatial tasks (Prather et al.,
13 2004) and different reference frames for visual and haptic tasks (Strother et al., 2016).
14 However, the present study cannot disentangle the two explanations, as it did not vary
15 the type of task (spatial vs non-spatial) or the location of the haptic stimuli with respect
16 to the body midline. Finally, the absence of statistical differences between grouping
17 conditions was expected, given that the low-level features of the haptic stimuli were the
18 same across the different experimental conditions.

19 4.3. Shortcomings, limitations and future directions

20 The procedure used in the present study could be a useful method for investigating
21 in greater depth the perceptual organization processes in a long-neglected sensory
22 modality. Future work should extend the grouping principles under investigation and
23 introduce each grouping principle as a multilevel factor, to draw solid conclusions about
24 the dominance dynamics between different grouping principles and the additivity of the
25 grouping effects in touch.

1 Regarding the analysis of the brain activity, ICA clustering made it possible to
2 separate and identify independent brain sources of activity implicated in the grouping
3 process. However, future research should address the coupling between the different
4 regions of the cortex to establish the functional relationship between those areas. At
5 least two different measures could be useful for this purpose. First, event-related
6 coherence (ERCOH), which determines the degree of synchronization between different
7 IC clusters at different frequencies and latencies (Lin et al., 2012). Secondly, the use of
8 Granger-causality models to analyze the information flow and infer the causal
9 dependency between different sources of electrophysiological activity (Mullen,
10 Delorme, Kothe, & Makeig, 2010). These two methods could constitute an important
11 tool to understand how the different brain areas involved in the haptic grouping process
12 cooperate, and the functional role played by each. Another important venue for future
13 research would be to study the cross-modal effects between sensory modalities in
14 perceptual grouping and their neural correlates, to investigate whether perceptual
15 grouping constitutes a multimodal process shared between sensory modalities, or, on the
16 contrary, whether it is specific to each perceptual modality. To conclude, it is worth
17 noting the potential practical applications of a better knowledge of how the tactile
18 perceptual scene is organized into meaningful objects in several areas; for example, to
19 design visuo-tactile interfaces or develop tactile resources for visually impaired people.

20 **5. Acknowledgments**

21 A Doctoral Fellowship from MECED granted to AP (FPU13/05914) supported this work,
22 and grants from the Spanish Government (PSI2013-41409-R and PSI2016-80337-R) to
23 SB and from the Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia (2014-028-UNED-
24 PROY) awarded to JM.

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